

2020-23

End of Project report

The Teach-Make project was fantastic to be a part of and I absolutely loved the chance to be fully immersed in it. The project allowed us to be creative, innovative practitioners as we had the opportunity to design a curriculum which included aspects of all different subjects – drama, art, D&T, music, science, maths and so much more. I loved exploring different ways to introduce new concepts, such as teaching forces through drama. This is most definitely an aspect of the project which we have used within the teaching of other subjects across our school since finishing the project. When making the learning in our project active through drama, we were amazed at how well the children remembered the technical learning and their meaning. This is also something which we have introduced across our school for teaching vocabulary – introducing key vocabulary for each topic through acting them out to aid their recall. This has proven to be extremely successful so far and the children have loved this new way of learning technical vocabulary.

Having access to 'experts' in different areas was also extremely valuable!

Headteacher

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Research ethics approval: University of Central Lancashire (BAHSS2 0081)

To reference this report:

Trowsdale, J. and Davies, R. 2023. Teach-Make: Coventry 2020-22 – end of project report..

1. Foreword

Imagineer is extremely proud of *Teach-Make Coventry*, not least for having managed, together with schools and teachers, to continue to run much of the programme throughout the Covid19 pandemic. We witnessed the struggles of teachers and artists who lost varying degrees of confidence in their practice and the challenges of the online workplace, but who adapted and generated new ways to support and work with each other. It is so heartening to hear and read evidence from teachers that, through using the TAME approach collaboratively, that they and their pupils have found confidence in more arts-based, child-centred approaches to learning. Teachers' case studies and the evaluation events show how they are placing themselves at the centre of a more investigative, inquiry approach with children, and feel somewhat freed from always being the person with all the answers and direction.

We were unable to add in the authentic learning opportunity for teachers to witness and work alongside artists and engineers through **Combustion** because the event was cancelled also due to Covid19. This would have provided an opportunity for teachers to draw on a live art-making commission, to see how artists and scientists collaborate and how this relates to a classroom commission. We are now in the process of building a new *Teach Make* cohort in Nuneaton and Bedworth Primary schools which will include this commissioning element with Artichoke and Imagineer for projects taking place across the Borough in 2024 and 25 including **Combustion**. This will enable us to evaluate the learning this opportunity provides and complete a programme of work and related research.

Jane Hytch, CEO, Imagineer

2. Summary

The project ran from September 2020 to Autumn 2023 involving 7 schools and 17 teachers. Teachers participated in up to eleven development days over the course of two years, along with skills development sessions and after school artist-teacher workshops (a full timetable is included as appendix A). These sessions included contributions from 5 artists from four arts organisations, and three STEM experts. They were supported by two academic educators. The programme had to be altered as the project progressed but retained its core principles (see section 3 on the implications of Covid19).

Evidence was gathered directly from teachers, artists and senior school leaders. Teachers participated in three interviews, artists and senior leaders in two each. Evidence was also collected through informal discussions at development days and skill sessions, and from a range of feedback activities about the impact of the project on practice and pupils. Ethical approval for this research was granted by the University of Central Lancashire ethics committee (reference: BAHSS2 0081). A fuller methodological note can be found in appendix B.

All teachers involved in the project were positive about the effect on their pedagogy. They were clear that they felt more confident and competent in using art-making practices as part of their teaching across the curriculum. This included more use of physical theatre/movement, storytelling, making, and drawing. Many also talked of the way the project has excited and reenergised them to embrace their commitments to more pupil-centred approaches. The impact on curriculum was less

clear. Although teachers were committed to developing their curriculum, they recognised the various school wide barriers to more 'wholesale' changes. Senior leaders continued to be committed to the project and developing arts-rich approaches to education across the school, but the increased pressures due to Covid19 and changes to working practices in schools made regular, direct engagement with the project and the teachers involved difficult. This led to less senior leader engagement than had originally been planned. As we noted in our interim report, where teachers on the project had a management role, this improved the impact of the project on school practices and internal dissemination.

Individual artists expressed both enjoyment and frustration in working with teachers. There was a clear sense that teachers were developing in confidence and experience of arts-based practices, and in their knowledge of how to use them in schools. However, artists were often frustrated at the speed of progress; this perhaps reflected a cultural tension between the sectors where teachers are used to being 'in charge' of their own classroom, in contrast to the more habituated experimental 'try it and see' approach of the artists. Artists developed a more detailed understanding of both the myriad demands placed on teachers and their approach to professional development (and trying out ideas both for themselves and their pupils). At the organisational level, two of the arts organisations have identified teacher development in arts-based practice as a significant part of their work, a third, sole artist organisation, continues to be involved in teacher CPDL.

The project also allowed for the development of a model of education, grounded in previous research in *The Imagineerium*, to be adapted to directly support teachers in curriculum design and improving pedagogy. The resulting approach, the TAME, has garnered interest from a number of organisations and schools interested in working with arts organisations to develop their educational practice. The approach was disseminated at workshops and been discussed at a number of UK and international conferences, as well as underpinning a number of academic papers.

3. Covid19 implications

The Covid19 pandemic had four significant effects on the project. Firstly, the pandemic increased the effort and stress teachers and senior leaders felt was needed to conduct their usual teaching and management responsibilities. This meant that teachers and senior leaders felt they could not give as much time and energy to the project as had been hoped. Secondly, it disrupted the internal communications within schools and communications and engagement across schools. Teachers were often 'bubbled' with teachers in the same year group or key stage. This restricted cross school conversations on development days and ensembles, and face-to-face-meetings with artists. All but one development day went ahead face-to-face, but with distancing and other hygiene processes in place. One development day was conducted online. Achieving this required changes in the order of activities, creative (and inspired) work by artists to enable practical arts-based activities in a socially distanced way, and changes in scheduling to allow more meetings when Covid19 regulations were less restrictive. Thirdly, and related to these two, senior leaders were, and felt, less involved in the project and the developing practice of the teachers. This was especially true of several senior leaders who were personally very supportive of the development of more arts-based practice in the school. Whilst senior leaders continued to attend the project management meetings (held online), their participation was more passive than envisaged. Fourthly, the management of pupils during the

pandemic, with increased individual working, restricted movement and less sharing of resources was at odds with the arts-based approaches the project was developing. The particular ways the artist had developed to work together and maintain social distancing were regularly used by the teachers in their own classrooms to retain some collective physical theatre activities.

This was an example of one of the positive effects of the project conducted during a pandemic. Teachers were able to experience and use arts-based approaches that minimised risk yet, at the same time, maintained movement and collaboration in the classroom. More generally, over the two years, these more arts-based approaches were welcomed as offering relief for pupils and teachers when restrictions were partially lifted. The arts-based approaches had a restorative effect, and motivated learning. Senior leaders were also clear that one of the impacts of the project on teachers was that it offered one element of 'normality' in their professional practice. The normal CPDL activity of the project was the one stable feature of teachers' professional lives, especially in 2020-21.

For the artists involved, the pandemic had a significant impact on work and practice. All of the artists and their organisations experienced wholesale cancellations of projects, a significant decrease in income and the need to furlough some or all staff for part of this period. For the artists not only did the project offer some normality, but also opportunities to engage collectively in their artistic practices. It also gave them to opportunity to be creative, showing how they could imaginatively enable teachers to overcome the additional restrictions of the 'Covid19' classroom.

As a final word on Covid19, it ought to be noted that most teachers and artists were unwell with Covid19 at least once and a number twice during the project. Further, all experienced friends and family members who were made very ill as a result of Covid19 and this, at times, impacted the project. Whilst it was not the only example, and many meetings involved sharing personal accounts, we were all aware of a teaching assistant who had died, and the fear and grief was apparent for staff and children. The Covid19 experience coloured and shaped the project experience for us individually and collectively, as a rare risk and opportunity to engage with others beyond our various homes and bubbles.

4. Delivery

The project was designed to include development days and two-day events for all teachers and artists to come together, and a series of after school 'ensembles' of teachers and artists either as individual schools or across two or more schools. As noted earlier, Covid19 restrictions meant that cross-school ensemble activities were not possible. Also, the majority of contact between teachers and artists was online rather than face-to-face. Both of these significantly changed the dynamics and nature of ensembles. As a result of conversations with teachers, we also introduced after school skills sessions open to all the teachers. These skills sessions focussed on particular arts-based approaches to teaching specific aspects of the curriculum, as requested by the teachers (see appendix A for a full timetable).

Teachers were commissioned to develop a new scheme of work for their pupils, trialling elements of it in year 1 of the project and delivering the full scheme of work in year 2 (or as a result of Covid19 limitations, in early year 3). Teachers were supported to develop approaches to systematic

evaluation in order to understand more fully the impact of the new ways of working on pupils' development. The evaluation strategies drew on lesson study and data collection processes used in *The Imagineerium* to complement teachers' usual approaches to assessing pupil progress. The schemes of work were aligned to specific aspects of the curriculum and the school development plan as agreed with their SLT. With this in place, teachers were given freedom to work with the Teach-Make team, to identify the approach, and limitations, that would characterise their scheme of work. These limitations and approaches changed over the course of the project, sometimes because of Covid19, but more often due to a range of 'everyday' contingent features of school life; for example, movement of teachers. In one school, a major school refurbishment during the delivery of the scheme caused changes to be made.

The development days included opportunities for teachers to work directly with artists on specific art forms and explore how these might be used in the classroom. The focus here was on skills development *as teachers using arts-rich approaches*, as opposed to teachers development as artists. There was also extended opportunities for teachers to discuss their development and the development of their scheme of work in cross-school groups. These were seen as very important as it gave teachers the opportunity to: share ideas and insights from trialling their schemes of work, recognise that other teachers were also underconfident, and consolidate the new approach through detailed discussions of the practicalities of day-to-day teaching.

5. Outcomes

a. Teachers

'It was a really innovative way of putting together a scheme of work where we are ... incorporating children in learning, where children are given a commission to create, and that commission brings in all their STEM learning'.

Developing schemes of work differently

The most profound impact of the project was on teachers' thinking. Whilst initial interviews identified a consistent philosophical commitment to child-led learning, most felt that this was in conflict with the 'prescriptive' nature of the national curriculum, levels and foci of accountability, and that they didn't know *how* to realise this ideal within the constraints of school, academy or national directives. The project was consistently seen as offering a practicable way of expanding how teachers thought about navigating these conflicts, enabling learning rather than teaching, about how the arts enabled them to facilitate children to have greater choice and input in their learning and giving them to confidence to enact such practices.

Most felt that the project had re-framed their existing thinking about what teaching is. They spoke of seeing teaching differently, of having developed 'a more open way of teaching' through the project and having 'the confidence to think a bit bigger than the normal constraints of the

curriculum’ or ‘just yourself or your classroom’. This was true for experienced and new teachers alike.

‘We were mainly focused on learning objectives and what’s in the curriculum – that was our driver in all our learning. It really took us quite a while to sort of change that way of thinking. But now ... it is more child-led... with an openness and a freedom to activities ... picking out those opportunities in their activities ... to address those learning objectives ... in those development days we were able to change the way we thought about schemes of work...’

‘As a new teacher, I was quite rigid in my thoughts – like I thought in terms of timetable ... “I need to fit all this into one day because otherwise I’m not going to get through it”, whereas [Teach-Make] is so cross curricular and I ... have a much broader sense ... I’m not as compartmentalized in my thinking or thinking that everything has to be done to like to timetable to the book the whole time’.

Teachers thought ‘normally SoW are designed and aimed at the end product’; ‘everything we work to in school is a finished end product!’. The TAME was seen as ‘completely different to how you would normally design a scheme of work’.

‘Yes [our TAME scheme of work] is covering the DT curriculum but it’s about the processes and skills that they build along the way... DT skills and learning behaviours – collaboration, problem solving ...’.

‘This makes you focus on the other parts of it that you wouldn’t normally – like the learning behaviours and what you want the learning environment to be like’.

‘We were focused so much on an outcome at one point that it was preventing us from planning a good journey’.

Teachers spoke of Teach-Make as being ‘brand new to me in terms of pedagogy’ and requiring a shift from the teacher at the front to being ‘more of a facilitator’.

‘In my teaching and my planning, I think I may be a bit more open ended. Maybe not so scared for it to be pupil-led or for it to be led in a different way.’

Another new teacher felt the project had given her a ‘focused but open way of teaching’, that she had become more confident and able to adapt and teach responsively as well as having ‘a more developed knowledge of the curriculum’ as a result of the planning process. She acknowledged that this had involved more planning because:

‘if you have a learning objective for one lesson, you have a set of skills you need to get there, whereas having, like, four different subjects and not knowing which ones

the kids are going to go down means there's eight different sets of skills that need to be covered to meet at least two of these'.

She valued this because she needed to know the curriculum and saw this more situated model as offering a 'deeper understanding' of it.

'No matter how well you plan the kids are going to take it a different route ... [which is] interesting to see how much they enjoy it'.

She described her thinking and planning as having 'a freedom that I didn't have before'. She spoke of also applying this in mathematics teaching, by saying to the children, "Ok this is the problem. Have 10 minutes to yourself. What do you think we need to do?" before beginning teaching in a structured, and therefore a more responsive, way.

The value of the TAME

Teachers saw the community of practice and commission as 'set[ting] the tone and expectation for what we want the children to achieve'.

'The commission ... leave[s] it very much up to the children to let them decide where they're going with it ... it's more around the behaviours ... having the knowledge in there, but making it more open in terms of the knowledge they take.'

'It's quite a unique approach of having the children sort of think about how they're going to behave ... or what sort of learning behaviours they might adopt.'

'The community of practice gets the children to feel a sense of responsibility and a sense of collective identity'.

Dominant in teacher accounts was a fascination with how the community of practice and commission generated positive learning behaviours and self-regulation, and how this constituted an internal classroom management strategy, minimising or negating the need for behaviour management.

Teachers spoke increasingly about seeing learning as naturally cross-curricula, that by situating subject knowledge and learning as necessary to the commission they saw 'how to amalgamate different things' making connections, not just across the arts and sciences but to all curriculum areas and thus of thinking about curriculum and pedagogy differently.

'The most exciting sessions for me were where the children are actually designing and researching ... not having any limits on it and it all being about their imagination.'

Hearing the experiences and ideas of teachers in other schools was significant in giving teachers 'confidence in delivering something someone else has trialled something first' and 'inspiration and ideas and affirmation ... that we're on the right track'.

The project invited teachers to explore creating and using different learning environments within and beyond the school building.

'Before it was very sat at tables and just very at the front teaching the children. Now I am, you know, taking tables away. I'm clearing the space. Lots of different materials and ... using their own ideas. Whereas before I thought it was you must follow this set of rules ... for this end product.'

Teachers found the exploration of how spaces can be constructed differently as:

'enlightening ... how you can adapt your classroom to teach ...differently... to use the school in different ways ... to think differently about the ordinary spaces'.

They used outdoor and community spaces and felt this helped them to 'think bigger when planning lessons'. They spoke of their practice generally being 'more hands on, more practical' with children 'getting up and about' and of 'pushing the tables aside and having a different space within the classroom'.

'Making the classroom space not a classroom anymore ... children as experts ... completely changing things so it doesn't feel like a lesson'.

Teachers saw their role differently, not as the expert 'at the front' but 'learning and discovering with them':

'facilitating the children and ... just guiding them ... I've tried to have that step back and watch and then observe the children and then step in at certain points where I think they need that guidance, but now it is more the children taking control.'

'I'm a lot more willing to be honest with the kids and if I don't know something we find it out together.'

The design of a commission, which is rooted in the world beyond school, situated children's learning as relevant in the broader world:

'it makes it real for the children ... they are put into a position where there's a purpose to their learning. They situate themselves within that and their experiences is what leads learning, and they remember their learning a lot more'.

Teachers spoke of children's:

'genuine excitement when you give them a real-life situation and context ... feeling like they really can do something and make a difference and create something that will work'.

And of their 'enjoyment in having a sense of responsibility', 'a role' embedded in the community of practice the scheme of work drew on and created.

Prompted by the Teach-Make team, in most of the schemes of work teachers looked beyond themselves to initiate and give status to the commission. For example, in one school the headteacher 'introduced the commission through a video' created of her in-role on behalf of an international charity. Another asked a city council lead for the environment to set the commission.

Another drew on consultations with a wildlife trust providing her expertise to inform how the commission was set.

Testing ideas throughout the process enabled teachers to experience for themselves and witness how art-making practices engaged learners and enabled active learning. They saw the approaches as not limited to the single scheme of work they were developing but that

they 'can be used in, across, all subjects'. Popular models of CPDL often offer directly repeatable lessons which meant that initially teachers expected Teach-Make to be the same and they resisted the work required to adapt ideas. However, over the course of the project, not being given a singular template for practice but principles and resources which required teachers to think about, make judgements and shape an idea as really appropriate to them and their pupils was recognised as generative, confidence building and vital to their development. 'You were constantly thinking "How do I apply this?" ... You were able to adapt it, remove it or build upon it'. In fact, one teacher commented that:

'this project can be as big as you want it to make it ... you could do it over the year if you wanted to .. picking out the things that you think would be more beneficial... making it the best for the children whilst also fitting in with the curriculum ... and the time constraints that you have in school'.

The teachers were unanimous in affirming the importance of the 'hands-on' skill development in using art-making practices in building confidence. 'The most useful things for us were the practical sessions' and 'seeing how we can use the arts more in the curriculum ... or be more practical in the way we think about and deliver subjects'. This was recognised as vital to engagement and 'keeping things fun... trying to include opportunities for them [the children] to be hands on and experience things as much as possible'.

'All [the artforms] have been really valuable ... I've loved the drawing, the movement, large pictures, DT, drama ... they're all things that I would remember and ... teach a class of children to do – it's all practically based – very good. Brilliant.'

Several admitted to having 'barriers' and not being 'at all confident to deliver art-making sessions' but of 'benefitting hugely' as a result of the 'bank of experiences, personal experiences to draw on'. Teachers noted how experiencing a range of art-making practices themselves helped them to see how such practices 'draw children out differently' and also engage different children differently or more deeply in their learning. Many commented on learning from the trialling of approaches.

'Seeing the children ... do something artistic ... not necessarily writing ... seeing what they did when they had the freedom, whereas [before] we'd probably give them quite a strict list of instructions.'

'I was able to plan in more physical activities for those confident kids who aren't necessarily really bookish; I was able to plan in art activities ... which my quieter kids are better at ... it was a lot more tailored to them and it did let them shine.'

In the end of project interviews, teachers were surprisingly consistent in seeing the importance of an extended CPDL process. Many were resistant to it being less than two years because 'we need time to digest what's been delivered we were able to take it into lessons and see if we needed to adapt anything'. Developing confidence with both the structuring principles of the TAME and with using art-making practices were central here. A quiet teacher spoke of:

'having the confidence [now]... to do things in a completely different way... that's been a challenge ... I'm at a point now where I can see why ... how it could be used in the classroom.'

In an evaluation session, this teacher shared a recent experience of having to plan a lesson quickly and at first defaulting to beginning with a template on the computer but then stopping and shifting to begin planning by using drawing and visual tasks. He and his colleague, whenever they needed reassurance, reminded us and themselves 'that children's engagement has been brilliant – that's a great barometer for success'. And beyond engagement into learning, a frequent comment was that 'they still remember what we did ... they can still talk about it'.

A strong theme was the need for a balance of the lived practical experience and the structured distilling. Teachers needed to experience the practice in order to deliver, as well having opportunities to dissect how the practice was structured and see in their own planning how the elements all connected in the scheme of work design.

'That first day we had the commission as it was like we were the children... we worked through it... Then the [design a TAME scheme of work in two hours] activity to bring everything together at the end ... having the [TAME] sheet was really useful to bring it all together in my mind.'

The TAME sheet mentioned here (see appendix C) was used in a 'Design a TAME SoW in 2 hours' activity towards the end of the project and was mentioned in most end of project interviews. This connects back to the point mentioned earlier that teachers learnt the value of being offered activities which could not be directly used in the classroom, but that they were required to make critical judgements about how particular ideas might suit a learning objective or how it might be adapted or

deployed. Teachers reflected in the second year of the project how they became more proficient and really valued the way 'the team would [help us] to tease out the links ... you made us think about things' with the result that teachers in turn were more critical 'being more discerning' about their use of particular activities in other, school provided, schemes of work. They were more ready to 'think as a team' with children 'giving the children ... a bit more ownership over what they're learning'. They saw the value of teachers adopting the role more of a 'provocateur, sort of instigating and sort of dropping things in'.

The issue of teacher direction and control was a strong theme throughout the project with teachers acknowledging their fear of lack of control and their delight in being surprised by the effectiveness of the model's structure. They spoke of:

'just letting the children run with it and the enjoyment they get from it. And we did the forest activity where they were constructing their shelters and the problem-solving skills that they have to overcome ... was just a natural progression ... and the things that they were actually coming out with were so interesting we just saw the children at totally different light'.

'Sometimes you think it's going to be chaos ... but it's just having the faith in the children to let them go and run with it and ... it's more enjoyable to watch them and learn ... more problem solving and collaboration, and that ownership of their task'.

'I find it a lot easier [now] to just let them get on with something and let go of everything having to be right ... letting them make their mistakes and learn through their mistakes and not always having to run to the initial plan'.

Challenges

The time that is required to invest in planning differently was a subject of debate between the teachers. Whilst worthwhile, many teachers saw the TAME process as time consuming. Some considered it 'quicker to adapt something that's extant - even if we recognise it's not better' whereas others saw that the pleasure of designing something bespoke that 'engaged students' and staff was a better use of time.

Teachers also noted that understanding the design principles and process of the TAME 'does take a while to get your head around'. As one said:

'we've done things with you and you start off thinking, oh well, where is this going? And then you realise the significance of it'.

This may have been a factor in their view that the length of the project was important in them having the confidence to 'stand at the front of a staff meeting' and train peers.

'Having two years [meant] we knew it inside out – we knew the purpose of it and we could really get that across to the other teachers ... because it's a new way of thinking for teachers.'

There was also a recognition that teachers' extended experience during the project was significant and that 'I think for other staff that haven't done that, I think that's going to be quite challenging [to understand]'.

Reflections included a view that the scope of study for their schemes of work could have been slimmed down earlier on to make planning less onerous in the context of a dominantly subject-based curriculum. They recognised, however, that much of the possibility thinking that enabled them to embrace the model might then be lost and this was vital to the scheme of work design.

'We had ... so many ideas .. finding so many ways that fitted with [our] focus ... so many avenues that we could have gone down ... synthesising that was really hard.'

Centrally, they identified the importance of time to develop confidence in a) understanding the TAME model, b) adapting and using the art-making practices proposed and also c) letting children lead their own learning.

A final challenge related to the resources and spaces available to teachers. They spoke of 'not having the tools and equipment to do more exciting work', the limited space to store such materials and tools, and the effort required to gather and manage diverse resources. Many were also frustrated, having experimented with spaces in the project, to have limited opportunities within the school grounds to develop these.

These challenges are rooted in pragmatics and require senior leadership support to address. Where SLT were engaged and supporting, challenges were or felt less significant.

b. Artists

'When the framework started to emerge, I think our practices were able to complement each other better, and become ... more integrated ... that was really important for the teachers to see our practices, not as separate things, but as how they would complement and build on each other'

The four core artists relished the collegiality of being a 'team ...working together towards a common goal', of 'working within other practices', and particularly when 'our practices had an opportunity to kind of merge and work together'.

They felt that they had 'broadened [teachers'] horizons' and that by enabling the teachers to play, 'they started to be more optimistic with what was possible' and to 'realise the benefit of playfulness'. They particularly remembered:

'where you were working with your teacher, and they suddenly have this really great idea that completely sat outside of their traditional sort of normal typical classroom practice, and that they were really excited about ... seeing their excitement in the possibility of what they might actually do in their scheme of work'.

This was most apparent:

'when they had to create a scheme of work in like an hour or so - those ideas were absolutely brilliant, ... and bought all those elements that they'd learned and we were all like "That's your scheme of work! That's what you should be doing! That's exciting, that's going to really inspire and change the kids!".'

The real skill of artists was in giving confidence and modelling responsive and adaptive practice to 'release people' to 'work in the moment', to 'not always know the answer' and 'think it through together right now'. Some artists also noted how, as a result, some teachers then became inspirational to the artists – 'new ideas came out a lot like a fountain and they embraced them'. Typically, here the support of SLT who 'gave permission' mattered. Artists really valued when teachers responded positively to the art-making practices and cultures they offered. They affirmed the artists practice, for example, by 'playing with' classroom spaces to 'design a space which actually prompts [desired learning] behaviours' or seeing how 'storytelling is [an important] part of learning'. Artist noted that the project was always a balance of the creative and the logical, of modelling and 'prodding'.

However, the impact of Covid19 was a significant challenge, firstly directly for artists who 'were all quite fragile from COVID itself ... as a really traumatic, awful period in all of our lives' but also for teachers, who artists felt:

'were so focused on their limitations because of the impact of COVID and we were asking them constantly to think beyond. And it felt like they couldn't imagine that there would ever be a time when they wouldn't be restricted, when kids wouldn't be sat behind desks where they would be able to move chairs and tables. And it just felt like we were asking them to imagine the unimaginable'.

'The teachers realised that actually, things were worse than ever, and they had to catch up. I think they all lost confidence ... all those great ideas fell out, fell by the wayside and a lot of teachers then played it safe. But then as the project continued, and actually that COVID19 Confidence bash sort of faded, then towards the end, those schemes ... they were much more brave with their decision-making because they thought actually, we can be a little bit braver, so it was ...that rise and fall a rollercoaster of confidence ...of their own capabilities'.

Another artist echoed that ‘there were some teachers who were just absolutely inspirational and didn't stop and kept on thinking - their trajectory was incredible’.

One, non-Covid19, disruption was in the churn of some teachers which for some artists made it ‘really difficult to maintain any kind of momentum’.

Observers and visitors to the project were impressed by ‘how artists made the group work’ and how ‘artists and teachers were being resilient through the Covid19 crisis, still coming together, still practising, still wanting this project’. This was echoed by the artists, one of whom said:

‘at the beginning, when there was a real adversity with Covid19, when we were all in masks, and social distancing ... I got a moment where I got really emotional, because I just thought, “Look at us what we're doing, you know, still, we're still doing it” ’.

The restrictions of Covid19 and need for repeated adjustment impacted negatively on artist development time with the result that in the first-year planning was often via online meetings and often ‘quite functional’. Whilst they recognised that we had worked to ‘find ways of building more’ in the second year some felt that this was underdeveloped.

‘We hadn't been able to do all of that really understanding the method and the model. It felt like ... we didn't really all understand ... the why’.

For one artist this affected how they felt their artistic practice could be maximised for the project because ‘we all have a very different route to get to [a particular] point’. Another felt that they ‘didn't quite know what was expected of me at times’. That the TAME was a model in development throughout year one was a factor here. However, as the artists affirmed ‘what's come out of it is a more confident project’, and this is being taken into future iterations, including Teach-Make: Nuneaton and Bedworth where we have begun by expounding the principles of the TAME and its deep interconnections with artists’ practice.

c. Broader dissemination

An expectation of teachers in the project was that they would engage colleagues in local CPDL as part of the usual run of such activities in their schools. This was an ongoing activity in school year 2022-3 and into the future. Some teachers have had the opportunity to work extensively with colleagues and a number of schools have adopted the TAME approach for some teaching across all year groups. One teacher commented:

‘I'm seeing teaching from a different viewpoint and supporting (colleagues) in being more creative in their teaching and approaching teaching in different ways apart from just standing at the front using the screen.’

In other schools the dissemination has been slower. This is influenced by two issues. Firstly, as we argued in an interim report different teachers involved in the project had different levels of responsibility and power. Where teachers had direct oversight of a subject area or key stage they have been able to more quickly implement learning from Teach-Make. Other teachers have had to depend on other senior leaders finding the time in the CPDL programme.

Secondly, all the schools are still impacted by Covid19 and catching up on the presumed 'learning loss' that children experienced. This has tended to be the focus of CPDL in 2022-23. We hope that this domination will diminish in future years.

The project team had several invitations and opportunities to work with the teachers to disseminate learning from the Teach-Make project. One of the schools in the project invited artists and educators to spend a day working with European teachers and pupils on an Erasmus exchange project in which they were partners. Pupils and teachers experienced a half day immersion into an arts-rich learning experienced designed on the principles of the TAME. This was followed by an afternoon spent with the teachers to explore the value of the approach. Teachers also joined artists and educators at an international drama educators conference where we conducted a panel discussion and a workshop on the approach. There was also an opportunity for teachers, artists and educators to lead a workshop at the Coventry Cultural Education Partnership annual conference.

Two of the artists had the opportunity to show and discuss the approach at an international gathering of artists and young people in Poland. Over the course of the project the educators have been able to present the approach and the research evidence on its efficacy at the number of national and international conferences (International Drama Education Research Institute, International Engineering Educators symposium, Bridges (International STEM and Gender conference), Coventry Cultural Education Partnership, European Educational Research Conference, British Educational Research Conference). This will continue with further presentations in January at the Association of Science Educators conference. Three peer reviewed academic papers have been published, with a further three in development.

As a result of these presentations, there have been a number of further opportunities to discuss the work with multi academy trusts, museum educational officers and other arts organisations. This included artists and educators presenting and leading a workshop at a Leeds 2023 Year of Culture event for teachers in September 2023.

Teach-Make: Nuneaton and Bedworth will be a strand of work within the 'Creative Explorers' project from September 2023. This will use the learning from Teach-Make: Coventry and offers the opportunity to work with a broader range of artists and other arts organisations to develop their work with teachers and pupils.

6. The development of the TAME

As noted earlier, the project was developed from the research conducted on *The Imagineerium*. That research had showed the distinct promise of the approach and has garnered enthusiasm from SLT for more use in the classroom. During Teach-Make, the project team drawing on the experiences and expertise of the teachers, were able both to refine the approach for use in the ‘everyday’ classroom and consolidate it into a model that was helpful for teachers in designing this type of curriculum themselves. The model, recognising that it is a distinctive ‘art-making’ model was named the ‘TAME’ (the Trowsdale Art-making Model for Education) and captured in the following visual.

The model shows the key constructing principles of a real-world ‘community of practice’¹ tasked to complete the ‘commission’. The language intentionally draws upon that used in the day-to-day work of the artists involved in *The Imagineerium* and *Teach-Make*. The model identifies the three aspects of a community of practice which teachers must give attention to and, in the outer ring, four key characteristics of the TAME are identified - active and embodied learning, using different spaces, a focus on stated knowledge and the deployment of maker-educators in the classroom (see appendix D for a more detailed description of the TAME).

7. Brief synopses of the schemes of work

The schemes of work, as noted above, reflected the concerns and particularities of the different schools and teachers involved. All used a variety of art-forms and stronger use of storytelling than would typically be the case in the schools. All schools focussed on design technology as each school saw this as an area for improvement. In addition, most of the schemes of work involved some engagement with either environmental concerns or wellbeing in the global south. It ought to be noted that early work on the schemes of work was conducted during the lead up to COP26, and this

¹ See Wenger-Trayner, E. and Wenger-Trayner, B. 2015 ‘Introduction to communities of practice’ <https://www.wenger-trayner.com/introduction-to-communities-of-practice/>

clearly influenced the foci. Schemes of work also drew on and enhanced pupils' learning across the curriculum, especially mathematics, science and english. What is clear from the extended discussions with the teachers is that the new schemes of work made extensive use of arts-rich approaches, which had been developed during the project and which were a significant change to their usual practice. There had also been for most teachers a re-appraisal of the significance of embodied learning. Another common feature was the use of physical theatre, often accompanied by large scale collective drawing tasks, to inspire and motivate pupils to see the relevance of the community of practice. It was because of this that the learning 'mattered' to pupils because it was situated in a context that 'mattered' to them. The artists had used this approach regularly during the project as a way to begin learning on the development days, and it had been used frequently as a way for teachers to represent and communicate their thinking about their developing schemes of work.

In one school, the teachers took the opportunity to overhaul a scheme of work which had low levels of interest from children and which, whilst fulfilling a curriculum requirement, had historically given rise to low-level learning by children. The original scheme of work had required the children to build a bird-box from pre-prepared parts following instructions given them by the teacher. The actual curriculum requirement is that children build a free-standing 3-dimensional structure, and the teachers started their planning with this as the focus of their commission. They were also keen to maintain and enhance the link to environment concerns. The teachers designed a scheme which positioned the children directly *as if* members of a community of practice of environmentalists with a commission to enhance their school environment by providing support for wildlife. The commission was open but set to require children to survey the school for wildlife, explore their life cycles, then design and build something to support a chosen wild creature. The teacher, acting as an environment consultant, could layer the commission through questions and direct instruction to ensure that children produced a 3-dimensional self-standing product as required by the curriculum. They could also support children in surveying skills, understanding the life cycle of particular wildlife and the science and design skills needed to build the final product. However, the experience of the teachers was that children were motivated to find out for themselves and quickly managed to work together in groups to fulfil the commission. The project was designed carefully to ensure that in the process of developing their products children achieved the core learning outcomes required by this scheme of work, the teachers maintain control and facilitated learning but by giving agency and clear, if bounded, autonomy to the children. The teachers used storytelling, especially to explore the life cycles of wildlife, as well as drawing both to design the final structure but also as a way of communicating ideas to pupils and between pupils. A fuller account of this scheme of work can be found in appendix E.

Another school began by drawing on the book they were focussing on for the half-term, a story of a child marooned on an island. The pupils were commissioned as an emergency support team who the marooned child could communicate with and with whom they could communicate (via written and audio channels managed by the teachers). They used physical theatre to bring the story 'to life' and instil in pupils an interest and commitment to the marooned child. Over the half term, pupils were given a series of design challenges that needed to be built on the island. The teacher was able to adjust and develop these challenges and the story of the marooned child in order to respond to pupils' interests and the areas of learning the teacher wanted to develop. The pupils were required to investigate what materials might be available on the island and create innovative ways to design a variety of structures necessary for survival. They, individually and collectively, drew and constructed

models, wrote clear communications to be sent to the island, all within the umbrella of an imaginative storyline. Teachers used a variety of drawing media and elements of physical theatre to communicate key ideas and gather responses from the pupils.

A third school focussed their attention on commissioning the pupils to design and build sources of renewable energy, especially a wind turbine. This was part of a wider institutional commitment to moving towards a zero-carbon future. Pupils were inspired through physical theatre to understand zero-carbon and its importance, as well as different ways to generate renewable energy. As a result, they researched the energy use of the school (and their homes) and looked at the requirements for different energy sources. Pupils used drawing in different media, and model building to develop appropriate designs. The design and build of a large-scale wind turbine occurred during a single day and resulted in a 'statement' structure in the school grounds. The teachers had designed in two elements which proved difficult to arrange in the timescale. The first was to make links with schools and scientists in Iceland so that pupils could discuss renewable energy in an international context. This seems viable to the teachers and may be part of a future iteration of the scheme of work. The second was to make the wind turbine a 'working structure'. Whilst in principle this is possible, it is expensive and would require skills not presently possessed by the teachers.

Another school addressed the building implications of the need to reduce carbon emissions, and focussed their scheme of work on redesigning Coventry. They commissioned the pupils into a community of practice of 'town planners' and familiarised them with the history of Coventry as a place which has been, historically, rebuilt several times. Using physical theatre, the pupils were encouraged both to remember the buildings and geography of Coventry today and imagine how it could be transformed to make it more environmentally friendly. Pupils used drawing in various media, including large scale drawings to develop their designs as well as modelling using cardboard. Finally, pupils used waste cardboard to build a large-scale model of the Coventry of the future, showing all the different types of buildings and features that enabled a reduction on carbon use, as well as being a pleasant place for people to live.

Two schools focused on water and its use in the global south. They engaged the support of different relief agencies to imaginatively position the pupils within a community of practice of 'water engineers' and as 'relief aid emergency support workers'. The water engineers were commissioned to design water and sanitation plans for remote villages. The teacher was supported by a close friend who was himself an engineer, which gave a sense of realism to the scheme of work. The teacher also made extensive use of the outdoor spaces in the school. This allowed pupils to investigate the ways water can be moved around. Pupils were also introduced to the specific limitations on resources in these remote villages which provided design challenges for them to overcome. Storytelling, using physical theatre and collective drawing, were used to inspire, motivate and educate pupils about the global south and designing water systems. The scheme of work emphasised the school's values of being concerned about others and their welfare. The other school focused on providing clean water in village in the global south, with an emphasis on sustainable water pumps and water filtration. Physical theatre was used to scale up the physical and chemical processes required for water filtration, as well as developing an understanding of microbial life. The teachers looked at ways for pupils to construct small-scale working models of ways to pump water using recycled everyday materials. Pupils had to design, draw, and then create these working models in the classroom.

The last school focussed their attention on the local, again on the environment, and linked this to broader work going on in the school related to its Roman Catholic foundation. Their scheme of work focussed on creating a commitment to be 'changemakers' in relation to environmental matters, identifying actions that would improve the local environment and ways to communicate the need for these action to other pupils, family and friends. They were supported by a local city council lead on climate change. Again, storytelling brought situations to life, and drawing allow pupils to explore alternative futures. Outdoor spaces in and beyond the school were used to see how human behaviour was impacting the environment, and small-scale activities, e.g. a litter pick, were used to show how small changes can improve spaces. The pupils used discarded rubbish to create sculptures to represent global environmental issues, linking the local with the global. This reflected work that one of the Teach-Make artists had been commissioned to do for a City event the year before, and which had been an inspiration for these teachers.

8. Next steps

a. Ongoing teacher development in Coventry

The Daimler Creation Centre is a resource for community groups, including teachers in the Teach-Make schools and their colleagues. Alongside in-school CPDL provided by the teachers involved in the project, the creation centre offers opportunities for teacher development (as funding permits).

b. Extending teacher development

Alongside Teach-Make, we were able to introduce a number of other education practitioners to the TAME. These include teachers from across Europe (via Erasmus), other arts-education practitioners at a number of international conferences, as well as teachers and other educators in the UK. We continue to pursue these contacts to look at ways to extend our work.

Specifically, a CPDL project for teachers in north Warwickshire has been awarded funding a part of the 'Creative Explorers' partnership. Over the next two years, teachers in the Nuneaton and Bedworth region will be inducted into the TAME approach working alongside a range of artists both in-school and in CPDL sessions.

c. Artist development

The Teach-Make project has developed the expertise of four artists at working in this way with teachers. Activities associated with Teach-Make: Coventry allowed us to work with a further two artists during the two years. Work on Teach-Make: Nuneaton and Bedworth will extend this group with a further two artists involved in the core team, but with the opportunity to engage up to a further 10 artists working on related 'Creative Explorer' projects.

d. Research

The development of the research base for the TAME is an ongoing project, specifically we are presently exploring:

Teach-Make: Coventry

- The contributions of the different art-forms embedded in the TAME to pupils learning, especially drawing and physical theatre
- The value of the TAME for supporting non-school based education, especially museum education projects and elective home education
- The value of the TAME in helping artists and arts organisations in their work with educators and as educators.

9. Appendix A – Timetable

Year 1

2020

23rd September - Introductory online session for teachers

2nd October - Development Day 1

27th November - Development Day 2 (online)

2021

23rd and 24th March - Development days 3&4

28th May - Development Day 5

9th July - Development Day 6

plus Learning Ensembles 3 per school (Online Imagineer and teacher meetings)

Year 2

2021

: 9th September - Skill Session 1

18-19th October - Development Days 7&8

15th November - Skills Session 2

16th November - Extra Development Day for teachers joining the programme in year 2

2022

13th January - Skills Session 3

14th March Skills - Session 4

17th March - Development Day 9

16th May - Development Day 10

7th July - Development Day 11

Meeting with senior leaders of all schools occurred every half-term.

Development, support and planning meetings between artists and academics occurred regularly throughout the project and were more frequent in year 1.

10. Appendix B – Methodological note

Data was collected throughout the project using a variety of media. Given that this was a ‘one time only’ opportunity, the researchers decided to collect and archive the maximum amount of data for future analysis. Some will only become relevant in the light of future research projects. Data was collected through:

- Teacher interviews (pre-project, end of year 1 and end of year 2)
- Artist interviews (pre- and end of project)
- Artist focus group (end of project)
- Development day
 - Videos of practice
 - Artefacts produced by teachers
 - Recordings or records of discussions
- Ongoing reports on the developing schemes of work
- Notes of artist development meetings
- Notes of meetings with SLT
- Notes from ensembles
- Notes and artifacts from skills development sessions
- Participant observation and researcher fieldnotes from all activities
- Discussions and material uploaded by teachers to the project Teams site

The data was used in three ways. Firstly, data was regularly submitted to light touch review in order to improve the Teach-Make project as it progressed. This focussed on the ways teachers and artists were engaging and responding to the project, and where specific comments were identified that we could respond to by amending the approach. Secondly, the data was used to ensure a full evaluation of the project. Thirdly, the data is being used to develop research papers and reports on the TAME.

11. Appendix C – TAME exercise

12. Appendix D – The TAME

‘An inspiring, intriguing and eye-opening project, which brings learning to life and ignites a flame of excitement, for teachers and learners’ (Teacher)

What and why?

Art-making is a fundamental aspect of human expression. *Teach-Make* is not just about making in the arts but locating art-making as the site for education across the curriculum. Whilst this means using more art forms as pedagogical tools – for example, physical theatre, drawing, model making – the approach begins with the curriculum. We start with a clear agenda setting meeting between teachers, artists and SLT; participating schools are invited to review their development plan and identify an area of the curriculum that needs enhancing. Teachers then reframe that curriculum area and explore how children’s learning can be developed by using the model of the TAME (an art-making approach). Teachers are supported in curriculum design, developing their confidence and pedagogical skills in arts-rich approaches to learning, and in evaluating the impact on children’s education. The culture and practices of art-making are harnessed in designing powerful and effective learning experiences – a point noted by teachers involved in a previous *Teach-Make* project. They also talked of the increased enjoyment and motivation of children for learning as a result of the structured freedoms and voice they experienced. One senior leader commented that the Year 4 class had described the TAME scheme of work as the best thing all year.

Teach-Make uses a distinctive model of curriculum development, the TAME approach. This approach emerged from a five-year research project on an innovative arts-engineering educational intervention for children in key stage 2, *The Imagineerium*. Evidence from *The Imagineerium*² showed a range of positive outcomes for children. Quantitative data identified that children felt more confident and capable as learners in general and specifically in those elements of the science and design technology curricula covered during the project. Teachers also assessed the progress of children during the project against the science and design technology curricula. They noted strong progression for all children and in qualitative comments showed surprise at the progress of those children they typically saw ‘disengaged’ and ‘underachieving’. There were general increases in motivation and increased interest in science and engineering as a result of the project. One child noted that she had not realised that engineering was both ‘hands-on’ and ‘mind-on’ which made it more attractive for her; others talked of being inspired and wanting to try harder at what they do. Further, the data showed that children developed transversal skills of collaboration, problem-solving and resilience having had the opportunity to practice these as a result of working together and being able to direct their own activity and learning. The joint conclusion of teachers and educational researchers was that the project had enhanced children’s learning and confidence in relation to education in general,

‘I wanted to sort it out – not leave it... Since the project it has come to me that you need to keep on solving problems if something doesn’t work... I just don’t give up .. I feel more capable of doing it now.’

² The evidence is reported in Trowsdale (2014; 2020); Trowsdale, McKenna and Francis (2019; 2021). Further, discussions of the approach can be found in Davies and Trowsdale (2017; 2021) and Trowsdale and Davies (2022; 2023).

motivated and driven an interest in integrated practices such as engineering, given greater opportunities for them to engage in arts-rich activities and supported them in achieving the learning outcomes required by national standards.

The TAME approach

The *Teach-Make* project commissions teachers and schools to develop a new scheme of work that will contribute to their school development plan. In this sense it models the TAME approach (see right) of a real-world commission and involvement in a real-world community of practice to not only develop a scheme of work but facilitate teachers' professional development. Two teachers from each school, with the support of a member of SLT, spend up to four terms on this project. Over that period, teachers will be supported in two ways. The first is a series of regular ½ day gatherings of the community of practice, all teachers, artists and educationalists. These gatherings will provide a space for critical conversations about children and learning, and develop teachers' confidence and skills in arts-rich pedagogical practices, curriculum design, subject-specific knowledge and evaluation of learning. The second is a series of regular school-based sessions of the artists and the teachers from the school to discuss and develop a school's particular scheme of work. Throughout the project teachers 'try out' particular ideas, pedagogies and ways of working with pupils, undertake a series of 'pupil voice' and evaluation activities in order to see how these work for them. These 'try outs' form part of the ongoing conversation between teachers from different schools.

The TAME approach has been tested and works for children and teachers in mainstream school. It has two key structuring principles and four key characteristics. In addition, the approach embeds a range of principles for effective education drawn from inquiry and project-based learning.

'Creating a community of practice can lead to changes in children's behaviour as they rise to the expectations of the role allocated to them. Collaborative activities and projects allow greater independence of thought and ownership of their own

The curriculum design is structured by an 'art-making community of practice' and a real-world task, described as 'the commission'. This conceptualisation of an art-making Community of Practice (CoP) has three elements: community, domain and practice. It focusses on a distinct group of people (the community) who are engaged in a specific area of activity (the domain) and who, as a result of their interest in and the character of that domain, conduct themselves and structure the community in particular ways (the practice). Art-making CoPs are characterised by a disciplined creativity directed at fulfilling a particular task, a community which values 'possibility thinking', collaboration and purposeful learning. The linking of the CoP and the commission

makes what children are learning *meaningful* and hence gives them motivation to learn. The commission is a real-world task that is ambitious and adventurous for children, but achievable. It is designed by the teacher to allow children to meet the relevant learning outcomes and in ways that they can scaffold children's learning journey. It therefore accommodates directed needs such as National Curriculum and local / school foci. However, it is also designed to provide a more fluid and

An Example

In one school the teachers took the opportunity to overhaul a scheme of work which had low levels of interest from children and which, whilst fulfilling a curriculum requirement, had historically given rise to minimal and low-level learning by children. The original scheme of work had required the children to build a bird-box from pre-prepared parts following instructions given them by the teacher. The actual curriculum requirement is that children build a free-standing 3-dimensional structure, and the teachers started their planning with this as the focus of their commission. They were also keen to maintain and enhance the link to environment concerns. The teachers designed a scheme which positioned the children directly *as if* members of a CoP of environmentalists with a commission to enhance their school environment by providing support for wildlife. The commission was open but set to require children to survey the school for wildlife, explore their life cycle, then design and build something to support a chosen wild creature. The teacher, acting as an environment consultant, could layer the commission through questions and direct instruction to ensure that children produced a 3-dimensional self-standing product as required by the curriculum. They could also support children in surveying skills, understanding the life cycle of particular wildlife and the science and design skills needed to build the final product. However, the experience of the teachers was that children were motivated to find out for themselves and quickly managed to work together in groups to fulfil the commission. The project was designed carefully to ensure that in the process of developing their products children

relational approach to education, and one which gives bounded agency and freedom to children to draw on and to develop their own interests. Children are positioned in an apprentice-like way in relation to the older more experienced members of the community. In particular, they can take a more watchful approach, as legitimate peripheral participants, such that they learn from the actions of others. A key feature of CoPs is that although learning can happen in formal teaching contexts, the majority of the learning is in relation to the real-world task. This can happen in learning-by-doing and/or through educative conversations whilst being supervised. In *The Imagineerium* children were sometimes supported to explore and learn about science, engineering, or arts largely by themselves, and sometimes, especially where there were safety concerns, they were directly supervised. At other times a more formal and direct teaching approach was taken.

In addition to the CoP and commission, the model foregrounds other elements of the integrated way of working characteristic of *The*

Imagineerium. Learning was 'active and embodied' in being more physically and cognitively active than in usual classroom learning and also in recognising that the mind is not disembodied and learning happens through and in the body. For example, children learnt about forces through their bodies and as a result understood different kinds of forces and their effects. Storytelling enabled them to make sense of, for example, the role of forces in different engineering solutions and to understand forces as part of their daily lives. Such storytelling allows children to begin to mediate the different narratives of physical ideas in the world and in the more formal context of the Science/Design Technology classroom. So, whilst the approach draws on traditional notions of 'active learning' which are common in inquiry and project-based approaches to learning, it also emphasises the need to move beyond these principles and take seriously all the ways in which

children (and adults) learn. *The Imagineerium* also challenges the homogeneity of learning spaces. In the project, children were encouraged to use a variety of spaces which facilitated different ways of acting and thinking about the work they were doing.

Occasionally, these were very different, as when they spent time in a professional making space which was messy, adorned with a wide range of different materials to use as they wished and with models in various stages of production. However, it also included teachers and children moving classroom furniture or making use of informal spaces around the school

for work. These changes correlated with increased conversation between children and a sense of both ownership and control over the work. The TAME encourages teachers to think about the potential learning resources that could be provided by the local community – sometimes family members but increasingly by local organisations that have specific educational activities, or beyond the locality, through virtual media. In the recent *Teach-Make* project, teachers drew on arts organisations, environmental groups, charities and those working with refugees to develop the real-world aspects of their schemes of work and provide specialist support for learning. The TAME model also asks teachers to rethink their role from ‘experts in everything’ to ‘co-learners with their pupils’. Teachers in the *Teach-Make* project talked of the joy of joining pupils in learning about something they had never thought about, as well as the lack of confidence they had initially experienced in taking this approach. Significantly, the teachers saw that pupils were more involved, motivated and learnt more through this joint learning.

‘Teach Make has given me the confidence to use a more physical and active approach by including movement in many areas of my teaching’ (Teacher)

References

Davies, R. and Trowsdale, J. 2017. The value of instability: lessons from reviewing how and why creativity and the arts might interact with STEM education. *European Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 4(1), 584-600

Davies, R. and Trowsdale, J. 2021. The culture of disciplines: reconceptualising multi-subject curricula. *British Educational Research Journal* 47:5, 1434-1446.

Trowsdale, J. 2014. *The Imagineerium Pilot Project - with schools*. Report for Imagineer Productions. University of Warwick. <https://jotrowsdale.files.wordpress.com/2015/10/imagineerium-pilot-report-full-final-july-2014.pdf>

Trowsdale, J. 2020. *Art-making as a site for education*. PhD thesis: University of Warwick

Trowsdale, J and Davies, R. 2022. A new approach in the making : reinvigorating engineering education in UK schools. In: *Proceedings of the 8th International Symposium for Engineering Education*. University of Strathclyde, Glasgow. ISBN 9781914241208

Trowsdale, J. and Davies, R. (2023) How a particular STEAM model is developing primary education: lessons from the Teach-Make project (England). *Journal of Research in Innovative Teaching & Learning*. DOI: 10.1108/JRIT-10-2022-0066

Trowsdale, J., Mckenna, U. and Francis, L. 2019. Evaluating The Imagineerium The Trowsdale Indices of Confidence in Competence, Creativity and Learning, Thinking Skills and Creativity, 32, 75-81
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2019.04.001>

Trowsdale, J., Mckenna, U. and Francis, L. 2021. Teacher evaluation of the impact of The Imagineerium educational project on the creativity of individual students: The Trowsdale Index of Teacher Observation of Student Creativity (TITOSC). Research in Education, 101(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1177/00345237211014559>

13. Appendix E – Example Scheme of Work (authored by the teachers)

Scheme of Work Title
How can we promote biodiversity and enhance the eco systems within our school environment?
Summary
<p>Our brief is for the children to support something which enhances and develops the eco systems within our school environment. The SoW encourages the children to think about their current surroundings in school, but also within the wider world. We are aiming for the children to be reflective on the ways they use the school grounds, parks, gardens, but to acknowledge that it is does not 'belong' to them, that they share it. We want the children to recognise and to understand the responsibility they hold as a result of sharing these spaces and consider how we can change our behaviours to make sure we aren't doing anything to jeopardise these spaces. Children are required to think about how they can ensure that the school grounds/ gardens/ parks can be adapted to encourage more wildlife into them, can new surroundings/habitats be created? Children will need teamwork skills (collaboration), joining skills (weaving, binding, woodwork) and design skills. We are seeking to develop creativity, independence and perseverance in the children, encouraging them to work in teams (taking responsibility negotiating, challenging and supporting) and take joint ownership of a task.</p> <p>We are seeking to develop children's imaginations and allow their creativity, without restrictions upon this. We hope for this to be in a broader sense and to impact across the curriculum. We would like for this to be a learner led project that is not focussed on a specific outcome but rather on a journey, which requires them to build skills of resilience and problem solving and continue to apply them across the curriculum.</p>
What <i>Commission</i> were children given?
<p><i>Your task is to design and create a structure that promotes biodiversity in and around our school grounds.</i></p> <p><i>You will be an advocate for environmental change, collaborating with others, using your ideas and skills to fulfil this commission.</i></p> <p>The commission was developed and refined when we realised we wanted to give children an active role within the project, as advocates for environmental change, yet also reveal some of the key learning behaviours expected: collaboration and imagination.</p> <p>The commission was revealed to the children after two previous sessions launching the project and putting it into context. The project was launched from a book (The Promise) and movement used to represent facts about climate change and the endangered environment, giving meaning to some important statistics. Our specialist Forest Schools teachers spoke about the commission to the children, advising them which environmental issues currently need considering.</p>
What Community of Practice were they part of?
A real community of practice in which the children are positioned as activists, who have a chance to make a difference to the world and environment around them.

It will be a learner led, self-directed project, in which children take control of their own learning and take it in their own direction, learning collaboratively from peers. What ‘behaving like an imagineer’ means will be shared with the children. Teachers will be facilitators. Children will work together in teams, developing learning behaviours of creativity, independence, resilience and perseverance.

What was your inspiration for this focus? How does it relate to the rest of the year curriculum?

We want our children to have a knowledge of the world around them, understand the impact we have on the world (which is their future world) and what we can individually do to have an impact or make a change. In the previous half term, the children begin to explore this when learning about climate change and the influential work of Greta Thunberg. The project will be launched from an environmental picture book called The Promise, which children will explore through animated story telling.

Our project has a strong DT focus, as we are linking to our DT curriculum which asks children to create a free-standing structure (the designs the children come up with will need to be free standing) and forms the basis of our Summer 2 term topic: Beast Creator. The inspirational figure for this topic is conservationist Wangari Maathai, who the children will research, and our Philosophy for Children enquiry is based around sustainability and recycling.

The children have studied properties of materials and forces and balance in Science, which will be crucial learning to draw upon when designing their structures. Additionally, they will develop on the DT skills used when designing pulleys in the Autumn term. They will also need to draw on Mathematical learning, including measurement and 3D shapes and will use Computing to support their research and design process.

What did you want pupils to *do*?

We want the children to recognise and to understand the responsibility they hold as a result of sharing outdoor spaces and consider how we can change our behaviours to make sure we aren’t doing anything to jeopardise them.

In this learner led project, we want children to develop creativity, independence, resilience and perseverance, whilst developing teamwork skills (taking responsibility, negotiating, challenging and supporting).

What did you want pupils to *feel*?

We want children to feel in charge of their learning and the process (they will lead it and take it their own direction), giving them the resources, responsibilities and opportunities to feel that they are capable of making an environmental change to the world and their futures.

What did you want pupils to *learn*?

- to understand how to strengthen, stiffen and reinforce 3D frameworks (joining techniques, design sketches, evaluating and modifying designs)
- to build robust structures, demonstrating understanding the effect of bracing, wide bases and how forces operate
- to understand that different materials have different properties (e.g. being flexible in wind, waterproof, whether and how it decomposes) and how this might be useful in their design

- to have a knowledge of the world around them, understand the impact they have on their future world and what they can individually do to have an impact or make a change
- to understand the responsibility they hold as a result of sharing outdoor spaces and consider how we can change our behaviours to make sure we aren't doing anything to jeopardise them
- to develop learning behaviours including: creativity, independence, resilience and perseverance
- to develop their movement skills (through drama-based activities) and teamwork.

What happened?

Active/embodied - drama and music used to launch project through text, artwork to explore the text, exploration of counter-balances using bodies, use of movement (and Maths skills!) to represent climate change facts.

Research & Development process – Forest Schools teacher framed the research process, advising the children on which environmental issues currently need considering and ways of attracting wildlife and biodiversity to our school grounds. Children came up with designs, considering strongest structures and shapes.

Children explored properties of different materials (foil, cardboard etc) and how to join them, without Sellotape or glue, by creating a shelter for a Lego man. Difficulties were explored together and structures were shared and put to the test under different conditions (e.g. fan, water). Children were then given opportunity to return to the design process, using new skills to edit or enhance their designs.

Children also researched different famous buildings and their structures (e.g. Louvre, Eiffel Tower). Together we thought about ways in which humans have built things in ways that wildlife can live/exist around them (e.g. living walls).

Children had opportunity to create a structure, using spaghetti and plasticine. They evaluated the challenges of this, thought about which were the strongest shapes and what a durable way of joining materials in their designs could be.

Children took part in a carousel of DT skills based on joining techniques. They then came up with their final designs on the computer.

Children negotiated to decide on a final design in groups.

How did you use *space* differently? (e.g. changing the classroom, using outside or other parts of the building)

Different Imagineering environments and spaces will be used throughout the project.

Parts of the project will take place outside - the children will use this space for their animated story telling and movement workshops – and our Forest Schools area (when gathering materials for designs and exploring existing Bug Hotels/hedgehog houses/bird houses).

We have Z chairs which can be taken and used outside easily when children are researching and designing. If inside, desks will be moved aside to give children the opportunity to work on the floor/add ideas to long rolls of wallpaper.

The school Imagineerium space will be used for computing sessions and DT sessions when children are building their final designs.

<p>Did you draw on the expertise of others? (e.g. other teachers, parents, local community, etc.)</p>
<p>COVID restrictions have not allowed us to have any external visitors in or additional trips this year, however moving forward we hope to draw on local wildlife expertise (e.g. a talk from someone at the Warwickshire Wildlife Trust, a trip to Coombe Abbey for a session about habitats).</p> <p>We have drawn on the expertise of others in school, such as our Forest Schools teachers and our DT lead. They have spoken to the children about habitats, natural materials, wildlife we have in school and helped lead the use of tools during the construction process.</p>
<p>How will / did you evaluate your SoW?</p>
<p>Evaluation of learning will be through journals. Evaluation of own/others' designs and ideas will take place throughout the process and evaluation of the final structure will take place at the end.</p> <p>Evaluation of learning behaviours developed, e.g. resilience will be gathered through pupil voice at start, middle and end (through emojis self-evaluation sheet). Staff and pupil voice will also be gathered post-project to see if there is evidence to show the development of learning behaviours.</p>
<p>Summarise what you found out</p>
<p>Children enjoy a greater sense of independence and are more engaged with the learning when given a purpose and more control over their learning. This independence goes hand in hand with building resilience and determination when facing an obstacle.</p> <p>Giving the children a role and purpose through an effective commission sparks excitement and engagement.</p> <p>Learning and teaching should not always be focussed on an end product – it is the learning behaviours and skills developed along the way that are the most valuable and important part of the process.</p> <p>To allow children to develop their imaginations, we must give them freedom and control (removing limits or boundaries) over their designs and ideas.</p>
<p>What was most difficult to manage?</p>
<p>Delivering the SoW effectively in an already packed curriculum. Having to narrow down the SoW – we would have loved to include more and spend longer on it, but this was not possible. Ensuring that relevant parts of the national curriculum were also being met.</p>
<p>What are your future plans to develop the SoW?</p>
<p>Further outreach to external expertise/a school trip to support and help frame project.</p> <p>Roll out of the model in all year groups across the school to enhance our DT curriculum.</p>
<p>Where are you using ideas and practices from the project elsewhere in your teaching?</p>
<p>Active learning through movement has been carried through into subjects across the curriculum. I have also found myself allowing teaching to be more self-directed and learner led, which has led to increased independence amongst learners.</p>

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The project was funded by the Paul Hamlyn
Foundation as part of their Teacher
Development Grants (cohort 3)

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